

RECONSTRUCTION OF A 3-D COMPOSITE BEHAVIOUR FROM A LOCAL APPROACH

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Abstract

This paper deals with damage and fracture of tridirectional composite materials. It follows out a work about a model for the homogeneous behaviour of this material. The aim of this work is the reconstruction of the homogeneous behaviour, using a model of local mechanisms which induce the material deterioration.

The different constituents are fibres, matrix and interfaces. Their characteristics are determined from standard and original tests in order to take the important modifications due to the fabrication process into account. Then, from simple physical considerations, we propose a mathematical model, which permits the restitution of the homogeneous behaviour from the one of its constituents. The parameters are identified and compared with different experimental tests.

Introduction

Among the variety of the composite materials, the tridirectional ones possess an important property : they have a great strenght in three directions of space. This tridimensional property is their main advantage.

The first step of the study of this kind of material was to understand their homogeneous behaviour. So, a mathematical model of damage and rupture was built up and verified with a 3D carbon-carbon from Aérospatiale [1]. It was a standard elastoplastic model with isotropic hardening and anisotropic damage [2].

The conclusions of this study were as follows :

- Damage takes a prominent part in the material deterioration and that, far before the rupture.
 - Then, in order to have a better understanding of the damage processes, it was interesting to study this material at a local level, that means : at the level of the constituents : fibres and matrix.
- It is the study that we present here. The scope of the paper is :
- A concise description of the material.
 - An experimental characterization of the constituents.
 - A mathematical model which permits the reconstruction of the homogeneous

behaviour from a simple ones of the fibres, the matrix and the interfaces. All the parameters are identified and verified with the 3D composite material above-said.

Description of the material

It is a tridirectional carbon-carbon composite. The carbon fibres are periodically disposed in the three directions of space. Along the direction 1, the carbon fibres possess a square cross-section, and they are made up with four strands of 3000 filaments each. The other fibres possess a rectangular cross-section. They are made up with only two strands of carbon filaments.

The voids are filled up by the carbon matrix. The density of this material is about 2.

Figure 1 : Description of the material

Global damage

The notion of damage is due to KATCHANOV and expanded by [7], [8]. Damage phenomenon is defined as progressive deterioration of loaded material and is revealed by a variation of elastic modulus. The evolution of damage is found by using cyclic tests. Here we introduce 6 scalar variables :

$$E_{\underline{i}} = E_{\underline{i}}^{\circ} (1 - D_{\underline{i}}) \quad \text{and} \quad G_{\underline{ij}} = G_{\underline{ij}}^{\circ} (1 - D_{\underline{ij}})$$

where $E_{\underline{i}}$ and $G_{\underline{ij}}$ are respectively YOUNG's modulus and shear modulus of the material in the \underline{i} set of fibres axis.

The experimental results have shown that damage evolution is really complex. Traction behaviour in the fibres direction is brittle without damage. In return, compression behaviour in the same direction is non linear elastic with damage. The damage law is given figure 2. Shear behaviour is identified by tension or compression at 45° between the fibres axis and the loading direction. We observe that damage in tension shear is larger than in compression shear (figure 3).

Figure 2

Figure 3 (plane 1-2)

Damage evolution as a function of loadings type

Some complementary tests (torsion test and compression in a direction outside of the orthotropic planes) have confirmed these differences between tension-shear and compression shear in the orthotropic planes, but they have shown too that damage phenomenon is probably more diffuse in the material that we thought in this first modelization. So a local study of these phenomena is needfull.

Experimental characterization of the constituents

In order to reconstruct the homogeneous behaviour of the material, it is important to know accurately the characteristics of the constituents. The problem is to define a typical behaviour for each. This behaviour must be characterized with some parameters which would be easily identified with simple tests.

The precedent studies have shown that the fabrication process modifies largely these characteristics. For example, the longitudinal YOUNG's modulus of the fibres seems very higher than before the fabrication. Then, the main difficulty is to measure these characteristics after the fabrication of the composite material.

Classical tests

Fibres behaviour. The geometrical structure of the carbon fibres permits to look at bending, torsion and tension tests. The specimens are taking out of the material by machining. Then, they are scraped and calibrated to obtain a regular cross-section [3]. On account of the different fibres symmetries, we suppose that the fibres have transversal isotropic properties. So, there are 5 independent elastic coefficients to determine :

Figure 4 : Carbon fibre

$$E_1^f, E_2^f, \nu_{12}^f, \nu_{23}^f, G_{12}^f$$

the other characteristics are given by the relations :

$$E_3^f = E_2^f, \quad \nu_{13}^f = \nu_{12}^f, \quad G_{23}^f = \frac{E_2^f}{2(1+\nu_{23}^f)}$$

The elastic HOOKE's law is :

$$\begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_{11} \\ \vdots \\ \sqrt{2}\epsilon_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_1} & -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} & -\frac{\nu_{13}}{E_1} & 0 \\ \text{sym.} & \frac{1}{E_2} & -\frac{\nu_{23}}{E_2} & \\ & & \frac{1}{E_2} & \\ 0 & & & \frac{1}{G_{12}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \vdots \\ \sqrt{2}\sigma_{12} \end{bmatrix}$$

Bending tests

This test permits the determination of the initial YOUNG's modulus E_1^{f0} , and of the rupture stress σ_R .

The experimental approach must be accurate to assure the quality of the results. In spite of all precautions, some local irregularities, and the bad alignment of some strands can explain the dispersion of the experimental results.

Figure 5 : Bending experimental system Figure 6 : Experimental results

Torsion tests

This test enabled to determine the shear modulus of the fibres : G_{12}^{f0} .

We use the same preparation of the specimens. However, the experimental difficulties are more important. Indeed, it is necessary to glue aluminium's head to hold the fibres and to apply the torsion load. This method induces often small alignments errors between the heads and the fibres.

On the other hand, it appears that the length of the fibres is a factor which affects the experimental results. So we must take these secondary effects into account in the results.

Figure 7 : Experimental torsion system

Figure 8 : Experimental results

Tension tests

Some tests were realized without satisfying results. However, we can observe that the longitudinal YOUNG's modulus is already well known with the bending tests. Moreover, the mixture's law is remarkably verified for this kind of loading and allows to confirm the precedent results.

Let us remind that the homogeneous YOUNG's modulus in the orthotropic axis is :

$$E_1^o = E_2^o = E_3^o = 120 \text{ GPa}$$

and for the fibres : $E_1^{f^o} = 484 \text{ GPa} \pm 8 \%$. The ratio between the fibres volume in one direction and the whole volume is exactly 1/4.

Conclusion

The classical tests which were realized, show that the fibres behaviour can be consider as linear elastic with brittle fracture in a first approximation. However, they are really insufficient to completely characterize the constituents ; effectively, we obtain only 2 among the 5 elastic coefficients of the fibres, and nothing about the matrix. Therefore to palliate these difficulties and to complete our understanding about the constituents, we use the results of complementary non standard tests.

Non standard tests

The matrix is elaborated at the same time that the material, under high pression and high temperature. The size of the pieces of matrix are too small $0,8 \times 0,8 \times 0,4 \text{ mm}$, to test it directly. On the other hand, its own nature does not permit to bring it out of the material. For that, we developed non-standard tests on specimens for which one fibres direction is eliminated by machining. With this new material, the classical tests adduce other results than those in connection with homogeneous behaviour. These new results can be connected to the characteristics of the constituents by a simple homogenization model. This approach enables to complete the determination of the matrix and of the fibres.

Homogenization "Method of layers". The classical and simple tests (compression test in the orthotropic axis or compression with shear) adduce only macroscopical results. So it is necessary to homogenize this new material to interpret them.

An homogenization entails the definition of an elementary cell :

Figure 9 : Elementary cell of the new material

The "method of layers" derives from the homogenization with asymptotic developments [4], about which the main ideas are reminded further. With the help of this method, it is possible to establish analytical relations between the characteristics of a periodical middle and those of the homogeneous equivalent material.

The relations above-said are particularly simple in case of periodical middle in only one direction. i.e., middle with layers.

Figure 10 : Layers

In order to apply this technique to the 3D composite material, that material will have to decompose in 3 successions of layers with unilateral periodicity.

Figure 11 : "Method of layers"

Experimentation [3]. The composite with "holes" is difficult to procure, particularly because it is impossible to bore the fibres in a long length. So, we choose the most simple tests : compression in the orthotropic axis and at 45° .

The experimental methodology took as a pattern the one which enabled to

determine the homogeneous behaviour of the 3D composite material [1]. In a first step, the matrix will be regarded as an isotropic elastic middle. So it is determined with 2 elastic constants : E_m and ν_m .

The compression tests are realized on specimens with longitudinal and transversal strain-gauges, about which the repartition enables to calculate the bending parasite effects due to the machining defects and to the appli-ance of the test.

Figure 12 : Description of the specimens

Figure 13 : Compression in the orthotropic axis

When the "holes" are in the same direction that the compression load, the behaviour is linear. The unload shows a permanent strain due to a sinking effect of the material. When the "holes" are perpendicular to the compression load, the behaviour is similar to that of the initial material : it is an elastic linear brittle behaviour without permanent strain. This is not surprising in so far as the stresses are essentially supported by the fibres.

The results are as follows : $E_m = 3600 \text{ MPa}$ $\nu = 0,15$. The shear behaviour is typically non-linear. The analysis of the longitudinal and transversal strains enable to measure the transversal YOUNG's modulus of the fibres :

$$E_2^f = 6000 \text{ MPa.}$$

Figure 14 : Compression at 45°

Conclusion. With this approach, we have a good characterization of the elastic behaviour of the constituents.

- The fibres are linear elastic. The two last elastic coefficients are ν_{12}^f and ν_{23}^f . They are of less importance and will be taken in comparison with the results of [5] :

$$\nu_{12}^f = 0,25 \qquad \nu_{23}^f = 0,45$$

- The elastic coefficients of the matrix are completely determined.

Reconstruction of the homogeneous behaviour

The homogenization which was used at present (method of layers) is a simple method to obtain the characteristics of the constituents. However, it is very difficult to introduce the phenomena of interfaces of fibres and matrix with this type of homogenization.

That is the reason why we preferred to use another method to reconstruct the homogeneous behaviour. Indeed, the non-linear behaviour of the 3D composite owes very much to the behaviour of the interfaces : fibres-fibres and fibres-matrix. For that, the classical results founded on the theory of asymptotic developments are used.

Recalling on the asymptotic developments [6]

In a periodical medium, an elementary cell is defined, the sizes of which are in the ratio η with these of the structures. If X_i are the sizes of the structure, $Y_i = (X_i)/\eta$ are these of the cell.

The displacement \vec{u} is a Y periodical function, modulated by the variable X , which slowly varies.

$$\vec{u} \text{ can be written : } \vec{u} = \vec{u}(X, Y) \Big|_Y$$

\vec{u} is developed with respect to η :

$$\vec{u}(X, Y) = \vec{u}_0(X, Y) + \eta \vec{u}_1(X, Y) + \eta^2 \vec{u}_2(X, Y) + \dots$$

where the different parts of the development are Y periodical.
As the deformation :

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\varepsilon}{X} + \frac{1}{\eta} \frac{\varepsilon}{Y}$$

In order to find the homogeneous HOOKE's tensor as well as the local stresses, it is necessary to find \vec{u} . [6]. This component of the \vec{u} development is obtained by the resolution of a variational problem.

Find $\vec{u}_1 \in \mathcal{W}(M)$, minimizing

$$\vec{u} \longmapsto \frac{1}{2} \int_M \text{Tr} [K \frac{\varepsilon}{Y}(\vec{u}) \frac{\varepsilon}{Y}(\vec{u})] dM + \int_M \text{Tr} [K \frac{\varepsilon}{X}(\vec{u}_0) \frac{\varepsilon}{Y}(\vec{u})] dM$$

and $\mathcal{W}(M) = \{ \vec{u} / \text{with same values on the opposite cell sides} \}$

On the other hand, we have the following results :

$$\text{It exists } H / K_Y^{\varepsilon}(\vec{u}_1) = H \frac{\varepsilon}{X}(\vec{u}_0)$$

The homogeneous HOOKE's tensor is defined by :

$$K^* = \frac{1}{\text{vol}(M)} \int_M (H + K) \, dM$$

the local stresses : $\sigma = (H + K) \varepsilon(\vec{u}_0)$. Note too that $\vec{u}_0(X)$ and $K^* \varepsilon(\vec{u}_0)$ are respectively the mean displacement and the mean stress in the material.

Applications to the 3D C-C. Method of approximations

The elementary cell of the 3D C.C. is similar as figure 9. It possesses three orthogonal plan symmetries. These properties enable to dissociate completely the different loadings cases. Any loading is a linear combination of six loading cases.

Three normal loadings and three shear loadings. This property permits too the transformation of the $\mathcal{W}(M)$ characteristics, for an easier using.

Main remark. The separation of loadings cases leads us to choose a primal formulation for the \vec{u}_1 problem in the case of normal loadings, and a dual formulation of the shear loadings. Indeed, a qualitative analysis of the material shows that the deformations are almost constant under normal loadings ; in return, the stresses are nearly uniform under shear loadings. So we choose to exploit these hypotheses for the formulation of the u_1 problem above-said. Remark that this hypothesis gives good results in the cases of 1D.

Simplifications. At times is the problem too difficult to solve and would require a great computer. Then, we choose to solve it with restrictions for the spaces $\mathcal{W}(M)$. These restrictions and approximations are consistent with the wished accuracy, and allow the obtaining of analytical results.

Results. In the simple following cases : \vec{u} and σ are constant by pieces, we obtain the homogeneous HOOKE's coefficients :

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} K_{11}^* = K_{22}^* = K_{33}^* = \frac{1}{4} \{ 2K_{22}^f + K_{11}^f + K_{11}^m - \frac{2(K_{12}^f - K_{23}^f)^2}{2K_{22}^f + K_{11}^f + K_{23}^f + K_{44}^m} \} \\ K_{12}^* = K_{23}^* = K_{13}^* = \frac{1}{4} \{ 2K_{12}^f + K_{23}^f + K_{12}^m + \frac{(K_{23}^f - K_{12}^f)^2}{2K_{22}^f + K_{11}^f + K_{23}^f + K_{44}^m} \} \end{array} \right.$$

with K^f : HOOKE's matrix of the carbon fibres,

K^m : HOOKE's matrix of carbon matrix.

We recognize the mixtures law (VOIGT approximation) which is slightly altered by a complement part. This part is here negligible taking the importance of K_{22}^f .

As, with σ constant by pieces, we obtain :

$$\frac{1}{G_{23}^*} = \frac{1}{G_{31}^*} = \frac{1}{G_{12}^*} = \frac{1}{4} \left[\frac{1}{G_{23}^*} + \frac{2}{G_{12}^*} + \frac{1}{G^m} \right]$$

It is exactly the REUSS approximation. With less limitative distributions of \vec{u} and σ , the results improve progressively.

with

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} Y = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Sigma} \frac{\sigma^2}{k_{\Sigma}} d\Sigma \quad z = \text{Ln } k_{\Sigma} \\ R : \text{hardening variable, and } \gamma, \text{ its dual variable.} \end{array} \right.$$

we have : $\dot{z} = \dot{\lambda}_p \frac{\partial f}{\partial Y}$; $-\dot{\gamma} = \frac{\partial f}{\partial R}$

and $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \dot{\lambda}_p = 0 \text{ if } f < 0 \text{ or, } \dot{f} = 0 \text{ and } f < 0 : \text{elastic behaviour} \\ \dot{\lambda}_p > 0 \text{ if } f = 0 \text{ and } \dot{f} = 0 : \text{non-linear behaviour.} \end{array} \right.$

Plasticity of the matrix. We choose a quite simple model which is written in terms of rate of strains :

$$\text{let } \dot{\epsilon} = K^{-1} \dot{\sigma} + \dot{\lambda}_p \frac{\sigma_D}{\delta_{II}}$$

where $K^{-1} \dot{\sigma}$: elastic rate of strain of the matrix

and $\dot{\lambda}_p \frac{\sigma_D}{\delta_{II}}$: plastic rate of strain of the matrix

$$\text{The criterion is : } \dot{\lambda}_p = \text{Tr}[\sigma_D \dot{\sigma}]$$

Therefore, we can express the tangential strength of the matrix for monotonic loading :

$$\dot{\epsilon} = K^{tg} \dot{\sigma}$$

It is from the tangential strength of interfaces and of the matrix that we apply the homogenization results.

Identification of the model. For the interfaces damage, the aim of the identification process is to determine a local relation between the shear energy in the interface and the strength of the interface.

The difficulty is that we must find these local informations from mean results. An accurate analysis of the cell interfaces and the results of compression test with shear (at 45°) allow to find these parameters.

Figure 16 : Evolution of the interfaces strength and tangential interfaces strength.

Conclusion. The resolution method can be resumed with the following description :

Figure 15 : Description of the resolution method.

Model of reconstruction

This model must take the non-linearities of the material behaviour into account. We can show, with simple physical considerations, that the fibres are essentially slipping relative to their own axis. So it is necessary to modelize the deterioration of the interfaces, with the help of a parametrisation of the shear energy in these interfaces.

On the other hand, we must modelize too, the deterioration of the carbon matrix, which assures the material cohesion.

Damage model of the interfaces. In order to write the shear behaviour in the interfaces, the \vec{u}_1 problem can be put in the form :

Find $\vec{u}_1 \in \mathcal{W}(M)$ minimising :

$$\vec{u} \mapsto \frac{1}{2} \int_M \text{Tr} [K_Y^\epsilon(\vec{u}) \epsilon_Y(\vec{u})] dM + \frac{1}{2} \int_\Sigma k_\Sigma [u]^2 d\Sigma + \int_M \text{Tr} [K_X^\epsilon(\vec{u}_0) \epsilon_Y(\vec{u}_1)] dM$$

where Σ are the interfaces between the cell constituents. We have too :

$$[u] = [\bar{u}_{X_i}]^+ - [\bar{u}_{X_i}]^-$$

and X_i is the axis of the fibre i . $[]^+$ and $[]^-$ stand for the values on both sides of the interface. The coefficient k_Σ is defined on the interface Σ . Remark that :

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \cdot k_\Sigma = 0 \text{ corresponds to a perfect slipping} \\ \cdot k_\Sigma = +\infty \text{ corresponds to a perfect adherence between the constituents.} \end{array} \right.$$

It may be seen that the evolution law of the k_Σ rules the interfaces strength, therefore the material strength and its damage.

For this evolution, we introduce a convex function of Y and R :
 $f(Y,R) = g(\gamma) - R - R_0$

The same experimental results permit to obtain the tangential behaviour of the matrix :

Figure 17 : Evolution of the matrix tangential strength and σ - ϵ evolution

Verification of the model. The model, identified by tests at 45° , has been verified on tests in the trisectrice direction. The comparison between experimental and theoretical results is given figure 18.

Figure 18 : Comparison between experimental and theoretical results

Corrected model. In order to take into account the influence of the hydrostatic pressure on the interfaces behaviour, it is possible to identified the characteristics law of interfaces strength as :

to obtain this result, the hydrostatic pressure p^s is used as parameter in the damage evolution of the material behaviour. Therefore, it is possible to reconstruct the differences between the compression-shear and the tension shear behaviour.

Figure 19 : Influence of the hydrostatic pression.

Conclusion

From simple physical ideas, a model has been built up. It enables to reconstruct the homogeneous non-linear behaviour of the carbon-carbon composite material, with a simulation of the local deterioration processes of the constituents : matrix, fibres and interfaces.

Therefore, it is a general approach of behaviour model of the composite that we propose. Indeed, with the knowledge of the constituents behaviour, we can provide for the non-linear behaviour of the material under any kind of loading . We develop presently some extended applications to the complex loadings. Certainly, it is possible to use this model for another 3D composite.

For that case, it would be sufficient to identify the parameters of the new constituents behaviour.

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